

Curating Covid-19 data in Links

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Motivation

Curated scientific databases:

- “databases that are populated and updated with a great deal of human effort” (Buneman et al 2008) such as IUPHAR/BPS Guide to PHARMACOLOGY (GtoPdb)
- Curation challenges: provenance tracking, archiving, annotation propagation ...
- Digital tools are usually hand-crafted for every curated DB — often with very stretched resources

Ultimate goal: programming language support for curation functionality

- Cross-tier web-programming using **Links**: a single language for web applications, program logic and database interaction
- This will reduce effort needed for curation software, so more resources are available for scientific aspects
- We have developed of a **prototype curation interface** for Covid-19 data using the recent **temporal database extension** to Links to explore support for **update provenance**

Temporal databases and update provenance

- Queries can be time-specific or about how data has changed over time
- Temporal functionality can be achieved by the addition of two columns to a table: the start of the time period and the end of the time period
- This time period describes when the data is valid and is application dependent: transaction time or another metric of validity such as validity in the real world.

Standard database update

Key columns	Other columns
K_1, \dots, K_n	A_1, \dots, A_m

Key columns	Other columns
K_1, \dots, K_n	B_1, \dots, B_m

UPDATE

$(K_1, \dots, K_n, B_1, \dots, B_m)$

Temporal database update

Key columns	Other columns	Additional timeperiod columns	
Key columns	Other columns	Time_from	Time_to
K_1, \dots, K_n	A_1, \dots, A_m	1 January 2021	end-of-time

Key columns	Other columns	Time_from	Time_to
K_1, \dots, K_n	A_1, \dots, A_m	1 January 2021	now
K_1, \dots, K_n	B_1, \dots, B_m	now	end-of-time

Case study: Scottish Covid-19 figures

- Weekly CSV files with weekly Covid-19 fatality counts for sex, age, health board, local authority, and location
- Each CSV file contains new data for (at least) one week and may contain updates to counts from previous weeks

Temporal databases and provenance queries

How many deaths were reported in the week of 5 July?

How were those deaths distributed across the health boards?

How many deaths were first reported in week of July 5?

How does that differ from the most recently reported figure?

Which health boards reported the most changes?

Cross-tier web programming

Curated databases normally a **collection of applications**:

→ Database, web frontend, curation application

Links: cross-tier programming language with language-integrated query:

→ Client, server, and database code written in same language

→ Database queries written in the same language providing well-formed and efficient queries

→ Language developed at UoE since 2006, with temporal database features recently added

Curation interface prototype: update decisions

Scottish Weekly Covid Data Curation Interface

Overview

Query ▾

Pending

Upload

Other ▾

Pending

Updates for the week of 2020-03-30 arising in the week of 2020-04-13

Type	Category	Week	Old value	New value	Change	Time added
All	All	2020-03-30	282	283	1	2021-04-15 12:39
Sex	Female	2020-03-30	126	127	1	2021-04-15 12:39
Age	75-84	2020-03-30	106	107	1	2021-04-15 12:39
AgeF	F: 75-84	2020-03-30	49	50	1	2021-04-15 12:39
HB	Greater Glasgow and Clyde	2020-03-30	106	107	1	2021-04-15 12:39

Accept all updates

Reject all updates

Consider each update individually

Continue

Updates for the week of 2020-04-06 arising in the week of 2020-04-13

Type	Category	Week	Old value	New value	Change	Time added
All	All	2020-04-06	608	610	2	2021-04-15 12:39
Sex	Female	2020-04-06	261	262	1	2021-04-15 12:39
Sex	Male	2020-04-06	347	348	1	2021-04-15 12:39

Curation interface prototype: provenance queries

Scottish Weekly Covid Data Curation Interface

Overview

Query ▾

Pending

Upload

Other ▾

Provenance

Data item modification history

Select category

All

Select week

2020-03-30

Lookup

The data item for category All and week 2020-03-30 has the following change history.

Week of Modification	Value	Date of Modification
2020-03-30	282	2021-04-15 12:39:27.549333
2020-04-13	283	2021-04-15 12:41:6.636032
2020-04-20	282	2021-04-15 12:42:50.027521

Continue

Data

Provenance: data items

Provenance: data categories

Provenance: weeks

Provenance: rejected updates

Data items with at least one modification